

A Rare Coexistence of Appendix Neuroendocrine Tumor and Colonic Adenocarcinoma: A Case Report

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Abstract

The simultaneous occurrence of neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) and adenocarcinoma in the gastrointestinal tract is rare. This case presents a 49-year-old woman with a family history of cancer, who presented with abdominal pain, rectal tenesmus and bleeding. Colonoscopy and imaging revealed a recto-sigmoid tumor. Histopathology confirmed a moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma, and an incidental appendectomy revealed a neuroendocrine tumor. She received neoadjuvant chemotherapy and radiotherapy, followed by surgery, including an anterior resection and retrograde appendectomy. This case illustrates the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges of managing dual malignancies in the gastrointestinal tract. The importance of thorough surgical and pathological evaluation is emphasized.

Introduction

Neuroendocrine tumors (NETs) originate from neuroendocrine cells and are found throughout the human body, from the thymus to the pancreas and the GI tract. They are termed neuroendocrine cells because of their properties that resemble both neuronal cells and endocrine cells [1,2].

NETs of the gastrointestinal tract are rare, and the occurrence of a NET and adenocarcinoma within the same patient is an even rarer phenomenon. Colorectal adenocarcinoma is one of the most common cancers worldwide, while NETs, though less common, are increasingly being recognized due to advances in diagnostic imaging. Incidental detection of appendiceal NETs is rare, often discovered during surgeries for other conditions [3].

This case report highlights the complex clinical presentation and management of a patient diagnosed with both recto-sigmoid adenocarcinoma and a neuroendocrine tumor.

More Information

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Case Presentation

A 49-year-old woman with a family history of pancreatic adenocarcinoma “mother” and rectal adenocarcinoma “uncle” presented with a two 2 months of left flank pain, described as a sensation of heaviness, accompanied by mild rectal bleeding and rectal syndrome characterized by tenesmus, straining, and false urges to defecate, along with alternating episodes of diarrhea and constipation and weight loss amounting to 6 kg within the last month.

On clinical examination, the patient was found to be in fairly good general condition with a performance status of 1. The abdominal examination revealed no abnormalities, and a pelvic examination was normal, with no palpable masses or traces of blood on the glove.

Colonoscopy revealed a mass approximately 25 cm from the anal margin, involving the recto-sigmoid junction. The lesion appeared as a superficial tubule-villous proliferation with an invasive appearance, highly suggestive of a moderately differentiated invasive adenocarcinoma.

Abdominopelvic Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) demonstrated a recto-sigmoid tumor extending from the upper rectum to the sigmoid colon, located 110 mm from the anal margin. This wall thickening invades the presacral fat space, along with centimetric nodules of the meso-sigmoid, as well as irregular thickening and enhancement of the pelvic peritoneal layer suggesting local signs of peritoneal carcinomatosis. This tumor comes into contact with the posterolateral wall of the uterus, with the loss of the separating fat interface. A mild amount of peritoneal effusion was noted. Lumbo-aortic adenopathy was detected and no liver lesions were identified on this MRI.

The chest CT scan did not reveal any secondary lesions. Tumor Markers CEA and CA19-9 were within normal limits.

Given the suspicion of peritoneal carcinomatosis, the decision was to perform a staging laparoscopy. Peroperative exploration showed no peritoneal effusion, no no liver metastasis and the presence of

recto-sigmoid junction tumor extending to the posterior-lateral wall of the uterus.

Given the locally advanced stage of the recto-sigmoid adenocarcinoma, the patient underwent neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, PRODIGE23 which included radiation therapy and FOLFOX (fluorouracil, leucovorin, and oxaliplatin) chemotherapy.

During chemotherapy, the patient developed intestinal obstruction and was managed with an elective colostomy.

Following completion of neoadjuvant therapy, the patient underwent a pelvic MRI that showed a parietal thickening, circumferential and partially stenosing, in the sigmoid colon, estimated at 9 mm (compared to 25 mm), extending over 90 mm (compared to 110 mm). The rectosigmoid junction is preserved. The thickening infiltrates the muscular layer. The fat separation line with the uterus is intact. Reduction in mesorectal and mesosigmoid fat infiltration, with the persistence of a satellite lymph node on the right anterolateral.

Figure 1: MRI Images Showing Parietal Thickening, Hemi-Circumferential, in the Recto-Sigmoid Junction

An abdomino-pelvic CT scan did not show any secondary lesions.

the patient underwent surgery. intraoperative findings: No peritoneal effusion.

No peritoneal carcinomatosis or hepatic nodules.

Presence of a tumor in the sigmoid loop measuring 3 cm, mobile and free from the uterus and other organs. Presence of an appendicular thickening with a suspicious appearance.

A retrograde appendectomy, including a cecal collar, was performed. Intraoperative frozen section examination revealed neuroendocrine tumor proliferation in the appendicular body with clear margins.

for the sigmoid tumor, an anterior colorectal resection and a manual end-to-end colorectal anastomosis were performed.

Figure 2: Peroperative Image Showing the Appendicular Thickening

Figure 3: Image Showing the Colo-Rectal Resection with a Green Triangle Showing the Tumor and a Yellow Circle Showing the Stomia

The anatomopathological examination revealed a persistence of moderately and differentiated infiltrating adenocarcinoma, invading the colonic wall up to the pericolic adipose tissue, with evidence of post-therapeutic changes (estimated therapeutic response of 60%). No vascular emboli or signs of perineural invasion. Colonic resection margins and colostomy site: free of tumor. No lymph node metastasis: 0N+/16N. Stage: ypT3N0. Tumor regression: Dworak thickening 2; TRG 3.

The patient recovered well from surgery, with no complications such as infection or anastomotic leaks. At the latest follow-up (18 months post-surgery), there was no evidence of recurrence, and the patient continued to do well.

Discussion

The occurrence of multiple neoplastic lesions has been recognized in medical literature for over a century. The issue was first described by Billroth in 1889 and later expanded upon by Warren and Gates in 1932, laying the groundwork for today's definitions and diagnostic criteria, as adopted by the International Agency for Research on Cancer. According to current standards, neoplasms diagnosed within six months of each other are categorized as synchronous, whereas those identified more than six months apart are referred to as metachronous [4, 5, 6].

The earliest documented case involving synchronous carcinoid tumors and non-carcinoid neoplasms of the

gastrointestinal tract dates back to 1949, reported by Pearson and Fitzgerald [7]. These tumors are often asymptomatic and frequently discovered incidentally during histological examination of appendectomy specimens, typically performed for acute appendicitis or other unrelated reasons. Such incidental findings are present in approximately 0.5% of cases [8, 9].

Neuroendocrine tumors of the appendix are generally small, often less than 1 cm, making them difficult to detect through conventional imaging methods like CT or MRI. Their indolent behavior, small size, and the limitations of standard radiological tools contribute to diagnostic challenges [10, 11]. Definitive diagnosis relies on histopathological analysis, often supported by immunohistochemical markers such as synaptophysin and chromogranin A [12].

Management strategies vary depending on tumor size and risk factors. For lesions smaller than 1 cm, appendectomy alone is usually sufficient. However, tumors larger than 2 cm or those exhibiting high-risk features—such as mesoappendiceal invasion—may require a right hemicolectomy. The optimal approach for tumors measuring between 1 and 2 cm remains a topic of debate. Overall, these tumors are associated with a favorable prognosis [13, 14].

Lohsiriwat's research revealed that approximately 1% of colorectal cancer patients had metastases within the mesoappendix [15]. Based on this observation, several studies have proposed performing routine appendectomy during colorectal surgery, particularly due to the difficulty in identifying appendiceal tumors preoperatively. For instance, Khan and Moran reported a 4.1% incidence of synchronous colorectal and appendiceal malignancies in a cohort of 169 patients undergoing incidental appendectomy, advocating for its inclusion in CRC surgeries. Similarly, Albright et al. supported this approach, highlighting its cost-effectiveness [16, 17].

Conclusion

This case underscores the rarity of co-occurring recto-sigmoid adenocarcinoma and neuroendocrine tumors and highlights the complexity of managing such cases. A thorough diagnostic approach, individualized treatment plan, and multidisciplinary team are essential for optimal patient care. Continuous monitoring for recurrence of either tumor type is crucial for long-term survival.

References

- [1] Ahuja S, Joseph KA, Zaheer S. Incidental detection of an appendiceal neuroendocrine tumor in a right hemicolectomy specimen for colonic adenocarcinoma: A case report. *J Surg Case Rep*. 2023;2023(7):rjad161. doi: 10.1093/jscr/rjad161
- [2] Saha S, Sarker D, Sharma A. Incidental neuroendocrine tumor of the appendix: Case report

and literature review. *World J Surg Oncol.* 2023;21(1):315. doi: 10.1186/s12957-023-02154-4

[3] Ahuja S, Joseph KA, Zaheer S. Incidental detection of an appendiceal neuroendocrine tumor in a right hemicolectomy specimen for colonic adenocarcinoma: A case report. *Int J Surg Case Rep.* 2024;91:110121. doi: 10.1016/j.ijscr.2024.110121

[4] Billroth T. Die allgemeine chirurgische pathologie and therapie. In: Reimer G, editor. *51 Vorlesungen-Ein Handbuch fur Studierende und Artze.* 14th ed. Berlin: Reimer; 1889.

[5] Warren S, Gartes O. Multiple primary malignant tumors: A survey of the literature and statistical study. *Am J Cancer.* 1932;16:1358–1414.

[6] Jensen OM, Parkin DM. *Cancer registration. Principles and methods.* Lyon: International Agency for Research on Cancer; 1991. p. 78–81.

[7] Pearson CM, Fitzgerald PJ. Carcinoid tumors; a re-emphasis of their malignant nature; review of 140 cases. *Cancer.* 1949;2(6):1005–1026.

[8] Yilmaz I, Bostanci M, Saydam M, Seki A, Eyi O. Synchronous appendiceal neoplasia of ascending colon cancers: Three case reports and review of the literature. *Turk J Colorectal Dis.* 2019;29(3):162–164. doi: 10.4274/tjcd.galenos.2019.24865

[9] Hermans JJ, Hermans AL, Risseuw GA, Verhaar JC, Meradji M. Appendicitis caused by carcinoid tumor. *Radiology.* 1993;188:71–72.

[10] Muñoz de Nova JL, Hernando J, Núñez MS, Benítez GTV, Ibáñez EMT, Del Olmo García MI, et al. Management of incidentally discovered appendiceal

neuroendocrine tumors after an appendectomy. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2022;28:1304–1314.

[11] Ofland J, Kaltsas G, de Herder WW. Advances in the diagnosis and management of well-differentiated neuroendocrine neoplasms. *Endocr Rev.* 2020;41:371–403.

[12] Bellizzi AM. Immunohistochemistry in the diagnosis and classification of neuroendocrine neoplasms: What can brown do for you? *Hum Pathol.* 2020;96:8–33.

[13] Pawa N, Clift A, Osmani H, et al. Surgical management of patients with neuroendocrine neoplasms of the appendix: appendectomy or more? *Int J Basic Clin Stud Neuroendocrine Relationships.* 2017;[volume and pages not found].

[14] Njere I, Smith LL, Thurairasa D, et al. Systematic review and meta-analysis of appendiceal carcinoid tumors in children. *Pediatr Blood Cancer.* 2018;65(8). doi: 10.1002/pbc.27069

[15] Lohsiriwat V, Vongjirad A, Lohsiriwat D. Incidence of synchronous appendiceal neoplasm in patients with colorectal cancer and its clinical significance. *World J Surg Oncol.* 2009;7:51.

[16] Khan MN, Moran BJ. Four percent of patients undergoing colorectal surgery may have synchronous appendiceal neoplasia. *Dis Colon Rectum.* 2007;50:1856–1859.

[17] Al-jaleeli AN, Hilmi MN, Alturfi ARA. Incidental synchronous appendicular neuroendocrine tumor in patient with right colonic adenocarcinoma: A case report. *Int J Health Sci.* 2022;6(S1):5190–5195. doi: 10.53730/ijhs.v6nS1.6037

